

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**REVIEW STUDY: MANAGEMENT OF URTI'S AMONG
CHILDREN,2020**Ibrahim Muqbil Alanazi¹, Osama Assalloum Alanazi¹, Manal Taher Hakami²,
Meqbel Majed Alshelawi³, Khalid hammad al shammari⁴¹Paediatric Residents - Arar Maternity and Pediatric Hospital²Medical Intern- Jazanuniversity³Medical Student-Medical University of Silesia, Poland⁴Medical Student -Shaqra University**Article Received:** April 2020 **Accepted:** May 2020 **Published:** June 2020**Abstract:****Background:** URTIs is a common disease with a high morbidity among children and resulted in repeated unnecessary administration of antibiotics except in the case of persistent infection and bacterial type.**Objective:** This study aimed at available and proper management criteria for URTIs among children.**Methods:** The online medical database was searched then the English articles from 2009 – 2020 were included in the review.**Results:** There were 28 studies included that answered the question about the available and proper management criteria for URTIs.**Conclusion:** this disease is self-limiting and the medications are used for treatment of the symptoms. Antivirals can be taken with analgesics but if there is no bacterial infection, antibiotics shouldn't be prescribed. However, early antibiotic medications could be administrated among patients with acute otitis media, hemolytic streptococcal pharyngitis, epiglottitis, or bronchitis caused by pertussis.**Keywords:** Management, Upper respiratory tract infection (URTI), children, KSA.**Corresponding author:****Ibrahim Muqbil Alanazi,**

Paediatric Residents - Arar Maternity and Pediatric Hospital

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ibrahim Muqbil Alanaziet al., **Review Study: Management Of URTI's Among Children, 2020**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).

BACKGROUND:

The infections of the upper respiratory tract (URTIs) are the most common analyzed sicknesses among pediatrics specially from 1 to 6 years. It has a high occurrence rate ranging from 6-8 infections per year and the frequency changes occasionally with tops in fall and winter [1]. The seriousness and recurrence of URTIs is contrarily corresponding to age, recommending a development in immunity through rehashed contact with causative infections [2].

During the repeated, or clinically extreme diseases, the physicians ought to consider an immunodeficiency. Despite being self-limiting disease, URTIs resulted in repeated unnecessary administration of antibiotics except in the case of persistent infection and bacterial type[3, 4].

Anti-infection agents are one of the most regularly endorsed drugs for the pediatric populace in primary health care facilities, with URTIs being the fundamental purpose for most of antibiotic administration[5, 6]. The improper and unnecessary usage of anti-infection agents is presently one of the significant general health concerns overall[7]. Anti-microbial opposition is an inexorably significant danger to worldwide general wellbeing, and it is the most genuine outcome of miss use of antibiotic[8, 9]. The proper management is yet a debate thus this study is supposed to review the available and proper management criteria for URTIs.

METHOD:

The data base was searched online for information related to the available and proper management criteria for URTIs among children then all the eligible English articles from 2010-2020 were collected, evaluated and included in this study.

RESULTS:

The study included 28 articles were included in this review that were published between 2009-2020 including RCTs, reviews, case-controlled studies and clinical trials.

- Symptoms of UTRI:

Upper Respiratory Tract Infections (URTIs) comprise of rhinosinusitis, acute otitis media (AOM), pharyngotonsillitis and laryngitis [10]. The symptoms of UTRI include cough, runny nose, congestion in the nose, sore throat, fever of low grade, headache, fatigue, sneezing, and pressure on face. The symptoms begin after 1 to 3 days after about week of exposure and may last up to three weeks[11].

- Pathogenesis and diagnosis:

Proper diagnosis and differential diagnosis of URTIs is essential for proper treatment and avoiding improper antibiotic usage. The existence of traditional highlights for rhinovirus disease, combined with the nonappearance of indications of bacterial contamination or severe respiratory ailment, is adequate to make the analysis of the basic virus[12].

Physical assessment and history-taking, quick antigen examinations, and culture from throatare useful in separation of the causative pathogen for intense pharyngotonsillitis. Manifestations could include nasal discharge, cough, ulcer of the mouth, diarrhea, congestion and oral lesions could be indicative for viral but not bacterial infection [13]. Although, manifestations, as gulping trouble, high temperature, sore throat, stomach torment, sickness, headache, heaving or soft plate's petechial discharge, expanded lymph hubs in the neck, and red fever rash propose intense bacterial pharyngotonsillitis, particularly brought about by *S. pyogenes* contamination [14]. In spite of the fact that differential diagnosis of the pathogen dependent on clinical manifestations and signs creates high concordance among doctors [14]. The throat swab is affordable, sensitive and specific in prediction of bacterial infection ranging from 50-76%[15].

- Management of URTIs:

The guidelines of the National clinical practice rules (CPGs) for diagnosis and treatment of children's URTIs have been created in various nations, for example, USA, Sweden, UK and Australia[16, 17]. However, there is a lack in the studies regarding the assessment and treatment of URTIs. URTIs are mostly viral in inception and self-restricting disease thus antibiotics should be wisely used in case of complications as bacterial sinusitis or pneumonia[18].

Improper administration of URTIs in children can prompt overtreatment of a self-restricting infection as pointless anti-microbial utilize could result in adverse reactions, opposition of pathogenic microorganisms, and expanded burden on families[19].

The objective of treatment for the regular virus is manifestation alleviation. Decongestants and mix of antihistamine/decongestant drugs can constrain cough, congestion and block different manifestations[20]. Among children, it's better to avoid using cough medications among children[21]. The antagonists of H1-receptor may offer a humble decrease of rhinorrhea and sniffing during the first 2 days of a cold[22]. First-age antihistamines are sedative agents thus should be used carefully among children. The usage of topical and oral nasal decongestants has moderate

advantage in grown-ups and teenagers in lessening nasal air route resistance[21]. Evidence-based information goes against the utilization of anti-infection agents in the treatment of the normal cold since they don't improve side effects or abbreviate the course of illness[22]. There is additionally an absence of persuading proof supporting the utilization of dextromethorphan for intense cough[21].

As indicated by a Cochrane Review, nutrient C can be utilized every day as a prophylactic for management of serious regular cold side effects with different doses. If taken therapeutically after the onset of manifestations, it can alleviate the symptoms but the higher doses have not confirmed clear advantage in trials[23].

Early usage of antiviral medications for flu can abbreviate the span of flu manifestations, diminishes the length of clinic stays, and decreases the danger of complications. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention regularly update the recommendations for the management of flu depending on epidemiologic information and antiviral opposition designs. The antiviral treatment for flu could be administrated during the first 48 hours from the symptoms beginning and don't defer treatment for laboratory center affirmation if a quick test isn't accessible. Antiviral treatment can give advantage even after 48 hours in pregnant women and other high-risk cases[24].

Vaccination is the most effective method of preventing influenza illness[25]. Also, early antibiotic medications can be administrated among children suffering from acute otitis media, beta-hemolytic streptococcal pharyngitis, epiglottitis, or bronchitis. Insistent rhinosinusitis patients refer to indispensable need for using antibiotics if symptoms persist [4, 17, 26-28].

- **Complications and prognosis**

The prognosis is favorable however it can affect the quality of life during the illness period. Also, among seriously complicated patients, it can result in high recurrence, morbidity and death rates. These complications are rare but they can result in serious illness including viral pneumonia, secondary bacterial pneumonia, sinusitis, and otitis media.

CONCLUSION:

In this literature review, proper diagnosis of URTIs could result in proper diagnosis as this disease is self-limiting and the medications are used for treatment of the symptoms. Antivirals can be taken with analgesics but if there is no bacterial infection, antibiotics shouldn't be prescribed. However, early antibiotic medications could be administrated among patients with acute otitis media, hemolytic

streptococcal pharyngitis, epiglottitis, or bronchitis caused by pertussis.

REFERENCES:

1. Easton G, Saxena S. Antibiotic prescribing for upper respiratory tract infections in children: how can we improve? *London J Prim Care (Abingdon)*. 2010;3(1):37-41. doi:10.1080/17571472.2010.11493294.
2. Fletcher-Lartey S, Yee M, Gaarslev C, Khan R. Why do general practitioners prescribe antibiotics for upper respiratory tract infections to meet patient expectations: a mixed methods study. *BMJ open*. 2016;6(10):e012244. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-012244.
3. Rún Sigurðardóttir N, Nielsen AB, Munck A, Bjerrum L. Appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing for upper respiratory tract infections in general practice: Comparison between Denmark and Iceland. *Scandinavian journal of primary health care*. 2015;33(4):269-74. doi:10.3109/02813432.2015.1114349.
4. Ferrara P, Cutrona C, Sbordone A. Which treatment for upper respiratory tract infections? *Ital J Pediatr*. 2015;41(Suppl 2):A31-A. doi:10.1186/1824-7288-41-S2-A31.
5. Hersh AL, Shapiro DJ, Pavia AT, Shah SS. Antibiotic prescribing in ambulatory pediatrics in the United States. *Pediatrics*. 2011;128(6):1053-61. doi:10.1542/peds.2011-1337.
6. Alanazi MQ, Al-Jeraisy MI, Salam M. Prevalence and predictors of antibiotic prescription errors in an emergency department, Central Saudi Arabia. *Drug, healthcare and patient safety*. 2015;7:103-11. doi:10.2147/dhps.S83770.
7. Llor C, Bjerrum L. Antimicrobial resistance: risk associated with antibiotic overuse and initiatives to reduce the problem. *Therapeutic advances in drug safety*. 2014;5(6):229-41. doi:10.1177/2042098614554919.
8. Roca I, Akova M, Baquero F, Carlet J, Cavalieri M, Coenen S, et al. The global threat of antimicrobial resistance: science for intervention. *New microbes and new infections*. 2015;6:22-9. doi:10.1016/j.nmni.2015.02.007.
9. Ventola CL. The antibiotic resistance crisis: part 1: causes and threats. *P & T : a peer-reviewed*

- journal for formulary management. 2015;40(4):277-83.
10. Zeng L, Zhang L, Hu Z, Ehle EA, Chen Y, Liu L, et al. Systematic review of evidence-based guidelines on medication therapy for upper respiratory tract infection in children with AGREE instrument. *PloS one*. 2014;9(2):e87711. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0087711.
 11. Biezen R, Brijnath B, Grando D, Mazza D. Management of respiratory tract infections in young children-A qualitative study of primary care providers' perspectives. *NPJ Prim Care Respir Med*. 2017;27(1):15-. doi:10.1038/s41533-017-0018-x.
 12. Thomas M, Koutsothanasis GA, Bomar PA. Upper Respiratory Tract Infection. [Updated 2020 May 5]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2020 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK532961/>.
 13. Langlois DM, Andreae M. Group A streptococcal infections. *Pediatrics in review*. 2011;32(10):423-9; quiz 30. doi:10.1542/pir.32-10-423.
 14. Yoon YK, Park CS, Kim JW, Hwang K, Lee SY, Kim TH, et al. Guidelines for the Antibiotic Use in Adults with Acute Upper Respiratory Tract Infections. *Infect Chemother*. 2017;49(4):326-52. doi:10.3947/ic.2017.49.4.326.
 15. van der Gaag E, Brandsema R, Nobbenhuis R, van der Palen J, Hummel T. Influence of Dietary Advice Including Green Vegetables, Beef, and Whole Dairy Products on Recurrent Upper Respiratory Tract Infections in Children: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(1):272. doi:10.3390/nu12010272.
 16. Wald ER, Applegate KE, Bordley C, Darrow DH, Glode MP, Marcy SM, et al. Clinical practice guideline for the diagnosis and management of acute bacterial sinusitis in children aged 1 to 18 years. 2013;132(1):e262-e80.
 17. Zoorob R, Sidani MA, Fremont RD, Kihlberg C. Antibiotic use in acute upper respiratory tract infections. *American family physician*. 2012;86(9):817-22.
 18. Cooke G, Valenti L, Glasziou P, Britt H. Common general practice presentations and publication frequency. *Australian family physician*. 2013;42(1-2):65-8.
 19. Bereznicki BJ, Beggs S, Duff C, Bereznicki LJAfp. Adherence to management guidelines for childhood asthma in Australia. *Australian family physician*. 2015;44(12):933.
 20. Kjærsgaard J, Anastasaki M, Stubbe Østergaard M, Isaeva E, Akylbekov A, Nguyen NQ, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of acute respiratory illness in children under five in primary care in low-, middle-, and high-income countries: A descriptive FRESH AIR study. *PloS one*. 2019;14(11):e0221389. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0221389.
 21. Fashner J, Ericson K, Werner S. Treatment of the common cold in children and adults. *American family physician*. 2012;86(2):153-9.
 22. Morris PS. Upper respiratory tract infections (including otitis media). *Pediatric clinics of North America*. 2009;56(1):101-17, x. doi:10.1016/j.pcl.2008.10.009.
 23. Rose MA. [Upper airway infections]. *Monatsschrift Kinderheilkunde : Organ der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Kinderheilkunde*. 2014;162(2):137-45. doi:10.1007/s00112-013-2965-9.
 24. Siston AM, Rasmussen SA, Honein MA, Fry AM, Seib K, Callaghan WM, et al. Pandemic 2009 influenza A(H1N1) virus illness among pregnant women in the United States. *Jama*. 2010;303(15):1517-25. doi:10.1001/jama.2010.479.
 25. Harper SA, Bradley JS, Englund JA, File TM, Gravenstein S, Hayden FG, et al. Seasonal influenza in adults and children--diagnosis, treatment, chemoprophylaxis, and institutional outbreak management: clinical practice guidelines of the Infectious Diseases Society of America. *Clinical infectious diseases : an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*. 2009;48(8):1003-32. doi:10.1086/598513.
 26. Hauk L. AAP releases guideline on diagnosis and management of acute bacterial sinusitis in children one to 18 years of age. *American family physician*. 2014;89(8):676-81.
 27. Chiappini E, Principi N, Mansi N, Serra A, De Masi S, Camaioni A, et al. Management of acute pharyngitis in children: summary of the

Italian National Institute of Health guidelines. Clinical therapeutics. 2012;34(6):1442-58.e2. doi:10.1016/j.clinthera.2012.04.028.

28. Kuchar E, Miśkiewicz K, Szenborn L, Kurpas D. Respiratory tract infections in children in primary healthcare in Poland. *Advances in experimental medicine and biology*. 2015;835:53-9. doi:10.1007/5584_2014_34.